

ANALYSING CLT IN TEACHING EFL FOR A2 LEVEL

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Abstract: *This article discusses the importance of communicative teaching methods in acquiring language skills and, consequently, in developing language skills to the point of growth.*

Key words: *action-based schedules, particular strategy, approach, "facilitator", grammatical patterns, Syllabus planner, Task-completion activities.*

According to the strategy of interpreting sentence structure and sound linguistic technique, British etymologists introduced communicative language learning (CLT). The current exam focuses on the recognition of educators regarding the creation of a CLT domain to improve the open abilities of stand-ins in schools. The objectives of the exam were to identify the insight of teachers regarding CLT in their classroom, to find out whether CLT improves the openness of understudies and EFL training in Uzbek schools, and to recommend measures regarding the creation of a CLT situation in the classroom. The instructor may limit himself to a certain strategy/approach, or he may use a number of indicative techniques / approaches, depending on the circumstances.

In the Uzbek environment, English is a compulsory subject at the school and college level, and the schedule of classes based on specific actions was introduced so that the understudies could master English. To make their display more successful, they also apply various procedures that include direct strategy, sound speech technique and full physical reaction, given the circumstances in which they are instructed. The prospectus is action-based, presenting four abilities and syntax in the setting. Having no status, teachers from different countries lack preparation for CLT, so they used their own professional abilities to abuse the exercises. They used the investigation materials available in the book, and no other constructive actions were observed. Since the places for the understudies were fixed, it was unrealistic to collect them. Despite this, in one live with movable seats, the instructor did not try to direct any collection work, explaining that he needed an ideal opportunity for group work more. Another explanation for the rejection of group exercises was that the understudies usually start speaking Uzbek, not English. In addition, in some classes, limited work in pairs was observed with a similar explanation that students, when asked to consider a question in pairs, begin to speak their local language. Perhaps the understudies did not have the necessary confidence or they felt constrained in communicating with each other in English, so they switched to Uzbek. This also reflected their low level of English proficiency, which was regarded by teachers in the survey as an important test. It was also noticed that several teachers who speak a similar local language used Uzbek to explain the consequences of difficult work or ideas. As expected, such circumstances prevented the creation of an important and intentional association in the classroom, the development of students' independence and the expansion of the possibilities of understudies for independent work or work with companions. On the other hand, the perception showed that the instructors sought to increase ingenuity among the understudies through the development of strategies and the use of AV tools.

CLT has become ubiquitous over the past forty years or so, and despite conflicting views on

appropriateness, its achievability has been tested in EFL environments around the world. In Uzbek schools, regardless of the specific requirements, there are an impressive number of English teachers who know about CLT and perform it in their classes, and, as a rule, female instructors are more interested in CLT to improve the physical fitness of their understudies. Another point of view on increasing the informativeness of the understudy is the educational plan. Recently, the vast majority of colleges in Uzbekistan have adopted an informative schedule focused on the use of language as a method of correspondence, in contrast to the standards of sentence structure. However, CLT cannot be successfully implemented due to specific requirements, such as huge classrooms, lack of AV facilities, problems with managing work in pairs and fees, as well as a low degree of students' English proficiency. *In the current study, an attempt was made to identify the recognition, practice and problems associated with the implementation of CRM in the classroom, regardless of its viability.

- Teachers can prepare CLT exercises, blackboard exercises and create CLT conditions to create informative opportunities for stand-ins.;
- By receiving CLT, teachers can make authentic correspondence the center of language learning; teachers can give students the opportunity to create both accuracy and familiarity with the CLT situation.;
- Teachers can combine different abilities, such as speaking, viewing and listening together, as this usually happens in reality;
- In the field of CLT, stand-ins can encourage or find rules for constructing sentences; the administration can organize advanced training courses for teachers to create CLT conditions;
- The administration can provide instructors with access to assets and AV assistance for the successful use of CLT;
- The CLT condition may convince the understudies, since they must pass, all things considered, the installation;
- The class size can be reduced/balanced for convincing CLT execution; For an effective CLT condition, evaluation tools can be created to assess the informativeness of understudies.;

The Curriculum Planner can be a planned language educational program that helps teachers in the formation of open skills in students. The student should get into situations in which communication takes place as often as possible in order to increase his communicative level.

Teachers no longer rely on actions that require repetition, accuracy, and memorization of sentences and grammatical patterns; instead, they require students to discuss meaning and interact meaningfully in a new language. Students should participate in classroom activities based on a cooperative rather than an individual approach to learning; they need to listen to their peers in order to successfully perform group work.

The teacher assumes different roles. On the one hand, she is a “facilitator, guide and assistant”, and on the other hand, a “coordinator, inspirer of ideas and co-communicator”. She talks less and listens more to the students' conclusions. In addition to this, the teacher also defines student learning strategies and helps students improve them if necessary and shows them how to work independently. Learning tasks become less important and fade into the background. This does not mean that they are not used at all, but they are of lesser importance.¹

¹ Oxford, Rebecca L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: what every teacher should know*. United States of America. Heinle & Heinle Publishers.

These changes give the teacher more opportunities for diversity and creativity, and she gives up her status as an authority figure in the teacher-student hierarchy. The teacher's responsibility is to be creative and prepare the appropriate material at home. The teacher can also perform other roles, such as needs analyst, consultant, or group process leader.²

Most of the activities discussed above reflect an important aspect of classroom assignments in CLT, namely that they are designed to be performed in pairs or small groups. It is claimed that by completing tasks in this way, students will receive a number of advantages:

- They can learn by listening to the language used by other members of the group.
- They will use more language than they would use in teacher-led events.
- Their motivational level is likely to increase.
- They will have the opportunity to develop fluency of speech.

Consequently, educational materials and classroom materials today use a wide range of classes in small groups. Many other types of activity were used in CLT, including the following:

Task activities: Puzzles, games, card reading, and other types of classroom tasks that focus on using language resources to complete the task.

Information gathering activities: surveys, interviews and search queries conducted by students, during which students should use their linguistic resources to collect information.

Exchange activities: Activities in which students compare values, opinions, or beliefs, such as a ranking assignment in which students list six qualities in order of importance that they could consider when choosing a couple or spouse.

Actions for transmitting information: they require students to perceive information presented in one form and present it in another form. For example, they can read instructions on how to get from point A to point B and then draw a map showing the sequence, or they can read information about a subject and then present it as a graph.

Actions with gaps in reasoning: they include obtaining some new information from this information through the process of inference, practical reasoning, etc. For example, drawing up a teacher's schedule based on the given lesson schedules. **Role-playing games:** Activities in which students are assigned roles and they improvise a scene or exchange remarks based on the information or hints provided.

Helping students understand the purpose of learning and develop their own purpose. The idea of learning as a lifelong process, and not as something that is done to prepare students for the exam.²

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